

Protestant working ethics and the spirit of feminism: A critique of Martha Nussbaum's capabilities approach

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Nussbaum's capability approach is based on a narrative imagination that propagates an autonomisation and certainty of salvation through work reminiscent of Max Weber's Protestantism thesis. Nussbaum illustrates this idea through her character Vasanti from India, in the wake of her liberation from her husband and work in an all-female company. To this end, she constructs a sharp moral gender Manicheism that revolves around the paradigm of violence. We interpret that Nussbaum's capabilities approach, far from being a new theory of justice, represents a methodologically questionable and logically contradictory gender lobbyism. Finally, taking Nussbaum's claim to design an Aristotelian social democracy as a starting point, we discuss the notion of ζῆλον συνδυαστικῶν (sexually dichotomous being) in his political anthropology and his clear rejection of political fantasies about states of nature and liberation.

Keywords: capabilities approach; ethics; feminism; Protestantism; salvation

This paper is devoted to Martha Nussbaum's capabilities approach as a developmental concept, presenting it as a unilaterally counter-gendered version of an old religious narrative that Max Weber characterised as the 'spirit of capitalism' in 1904–1905, and whose evaluation remains deeply ambivalent with him. Methodologically, I deconstruct Nussbaum's narrative imagination, which according to my thesis presents itself as a counter-gendered-modernised version of Weber's thesis. In particular, Weber's concepts of a *status naturae* or *status gratiae* – borrowed from scholastic speculations on the state of nature – and their gendered perspective are deconstructed. Nussbaum takes up Weber's spiritual-emancipatory concept of a metaphysics of labour in her figure of Vasanti. However, she inverts Weber's gender perspective and radicalises it into an untheorised ethical gender Manicheism *ex-ante*. In doing so, the ambivalences of Weber's balance are lost; neither on the psychological-individual nor on the historical-teleological-collective level does Nussbaum reflect on the price of a saving and healing authorisation through work. Like a psychological or political developmental approach that would go beyond sheer gender lobbyism on its behalf; her capabilities narrative is therefore hardly suitable.

The exoticist indeterminacy of the Capabilities Approach (CA)

The US classical philologist Martha Nussbaum (b. 1947) has further developed an approach of Amartya Sen in international cooperation (formerly called 'development aid') called capabilities approach (CA; Nussbaum, 2011; for a good introduction see Robeyns, 2016). Traditional psychological and political developmental thinking, she argues: 'has been too abstractly technical, fixated on nation-state collective increases in the gross domestic product (GDP), without attending to the living standards of their poorer inhabitants, and without addressing issues such as health and education, which typically do not [sic] improve with economic growth, ' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. ix) Her approach focused instead on the question what are people able ' (a.) to do and (b.) to be? ' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. x). *Doing* refers to their social functions ('functions '), being refers to possibilities to realise goals ('capabilities '). Her approach, she argues, be able ' (to) show respect for real people, rather than simply reflecting the biases of intellectual elites. ' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. x) Easily understood proclamations and moral commitment are commendable in regulated markets such as the academy and international cooperation, but they are no substitute for a contradiction free, theoretically coherent method and material elaboration. So what exactly are capabilities?

Nussbaum refers to the normative character of her theory, which, however, is neither metaphysical nor dogmatic nor logical, but quasi-empirically legitimised by an 'especially deep and continuous sort of experiential and historical truth, ' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 74). Its normative claim is, therefore, on the one hand, politically discursively expandable or *restrictable* (so that its 10-point capabilities list is also repeatedly rearranged), but should, on the other hand, also be understood in an irreducibly humanistic-universalistic way. This methodological indeterminacy and partial contradictoriness has been criticised on various occasions; some points of criticism may be named (see overview in Robeyns, 2016; see the following points in Claassen, 2010; Deneulin, 2002; Nelson, 2008; Qizilbash, 2011;): Are capabilities classic *civil rights of defence* or are they new *entitlements*? Where exactly does the (whose) line between 'basic ' and 'more advanced ' capabilities run? What is the conversion-factor-relationship between concrete capabilities such as life, health, emotions, thought or play, especially in the case of conflict (e.g., between emotions, thought and play)? How should pondering and aggregation be done, by whom, and with what legitimacy? What is the relationship between individual well-being and social responsibility, traditionally: civic rights and duties? Which authority should legitimise the normative character of the capabilities approach, and which should guarantee a balance between democratic discourse with decision-making on the one hand and diversity on the other?

The comments on these issues are highly contradictory in the literature, and it is difficult to discern a prevailing opinion: Clark, for instance, criticises this lack of inner coherence and stringency, Nussbaum's list of capabilities, he insists, is in fact an enticing, philosophical-mythological catalogue of virtues, methodologically 'Socratic intuitivism' (Clark, 2013, p. 176), politically Aristotelian social democracy (according to Nussbaum herself): 'There are certainly few references to how [...] 'other voices' [i.e., the voices of her worldwide, especially female interlocutors] have shaped the list [of capabilities]' summarises Clark (2013, p. 177) this discrepancy between methodological aleatory and political dogmatics, and Jaggar (2006, p. 314) adds: 'I have found no place in her extensive writings on capabilities where she questions her authority to decide what should be included on the list and what excluded from it, [...] she assumes the prerogative of assessing [others' contributions] moral worth, thus deciding whose opinions should be respected and whose should be rejected as mistaken and corrupt.'

Methodologically, it is indeed astonishing that Nussbaum does not quote her informants once in transcribed *verbatim* speech, ignoring the now widely differentiated standard procedures of qualitative social science research and vivid narrative art alike (Kowal & O'Connell, 2010; Koschorke, 2012); Vasanti's ex-husband,

though the starting point of the narrative, is not even given a pseudonym. Instead, the introduction of her character Vasanti is almost reminiscent of an auction: ‘First, we would probably notice how small Vasanti is, and we would initially take this as evidence of poor nutrition in childhood. [...] Because Vasanti has had no formal education she is cut off from a full understanding [sic] of her nation’s history and its political and economic structure. (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 4/7)

Critical nuances are communicated in a coldly detached tone, ‘such women [meaning her informant Vasanti!] (...) are often homophobic and thus unlikely to be involved in lesbian relationships (...).’ (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 11) This invisibility of her informant is all the more astonishing since the CA programmatically focuses on individual perspectives and self-perception, women’s voices, and not on externally measurable psychological, economic, educational, sanitary or other achievements, such as GDP, supply or literacy rates. Methodologically, it should therefore be recalled once again that Nussbaum is not a social scientist, but a classical philologist who, moreover, wants her approach to be understood melioristically-pragmatically, not epistemologically-theoretically. Robeyn (2016) comments: ‘the practical approach to political philosophy [i.e., the CA] also aims to respect truth (in so far as this is known) in its analyses, but is willing to make some simplifications and [...] compromises to move the analysis forward to the realm of practical recommendations.’

In the context of our investigation, we, therefore, propose to understand Nussbaum’s *Capabilities Approach* methodologically primarily as a narrative in the sense of Lyotard (Herman et al., 2005; Lyotard, 1979), which makes use of existing narrative elements to reassemble them according to the intentions of the ‘author’ and to assert a claim to truth as a claim to power. Koschorke defines narrative in this sense as a ‘narrative form’ that can be filled out in a meaningful way by different narrators, but in doing so is under the ‘gravitational pull of culture-shaping narratives’ (Koschorke, 2012, p. 38); Nussbaum herself speaks of ‘storytelling’ and ‘narrative imagination’. The narratives we are deconstructing are the Calvinist notion of certainty of salvation through autonomous work as formulated by Max Weber, and the Enlightenment’s narrative of liberation and natural law, as in Rousseau or Karl Marx as ‘culture-pedagogical narratives’ (Bobbio, 2016). Deconstruction, in this respect, also begins here with the poststructuralist question *Qui le dit?*

We hypothesise that the White, Protestant-socialised, arriviste woman Martha Nussbaum draws on Calvinism’s narrative of meaning-making and distinction through work (common intellectual property in the US as the ‘Weber thesis’), that she combines this with Enlightenment’s natural law metaphors of liberation, and that her genuine contribution consists in the admixture of an untheorized gender Manicheism. In terms of narrative technique, she makes use of some elements of the *exoticism* that 19th-century French literature in particular produced. Jean-Marie Guyau (1854–1888), for example, recommended in his *L’art au point de vue sociologique* (1887) the admixture of exotic, biblical, and antique elements for realistic narratives as *moyens d’échapper au trivial* (means to evade the trivial; Guyau, 1887, p. 95); exotic, biblical, and antique colouration became a means to lend vividness and depth to trivialities. Sexual and sexual-political themes were especially typical of the genre, such as the abduction of a White European woman to the Orient and the possibilities of her subjugation and/or liberation. Voyeuristic triviality and/or (sexual) political appeals, could thus, exotically ‘hidden’, gain depth and brilliance. An anticizing invocation of Aristotle as a precursor of social democracy could also be interpreted in this way, as well as her Biblical connotations.

In sum, Nussbaum’s CA remains shimmeringly indeterminate in method and content. I propose to understand it primarily as a narrative imagination in the sense of a realistic-exoticist narrative with strong moralistic intentions.

Weber’s spirit of capitalism and the status *gratiae*

The German sociologist Max Weber (1864–1920) derived the spirit of capitalist acquisitiveness from a specifically Protestant work ethic, which, especially in areas dominated by Reformed Calvinist denominations (such as parts of Great Britain and the United States), had led to a kind of ‘religion of work’ on which contemporary capitalism and its division of labour rested. In one’s profession (German: *Beruf*) – whose meaning is etymologically derived from ‘calling’ and whose religious-metaphysical exaltation goes back to Luther’s translation of the Bible (in detail philologically Weber, 1904, fn. 54 et al.; hereafter cited as PEGK) – the Protestant believer’s inner-worldly search for meaning is fulfilled.

If we (...) follow the word historically and through the cultural languages, it becomes apparent, first of all, that the predominantly Catholic peoples, just as little as classical antiquity, have no expression of similar colouring for what we call ‘profession’ (in the sense of position in life, the circumscribed

field of work), while it exists among all predominantly Protestant peoples. (PEGK, all translations by the author)

It is based on a paradoxically areligious-monkish asceticism, which extended to an auto disciplining through rationalisation of all areas of life, and which - increasingly stripped of religious terminology, but all the more unconditionally connected to it in terms of content - becomes the dominant characteristic of European-American modernity. Weber uses two terms of theological anthropology to characterise this so-called 'vocational' rationality and its counterpart: *status gratiae*, as a state of being chosen and redeemed, and *status naturae*, as the epitome of the merely evolutionary-biological constitution.

For only in a fundamental transformation of the meaning of the whole life in every hour and every action could the work of grace prove itself as a lifting of man from *status naturae* into *status gratiae*. The life of the 'saint' was directed exclusively to a transcendent goal: beatitude, but for this very reason it was thoroughly rationalised in its this-worldly course (...). (PEGK, *italics* original)

Weber's distinction, as a 'discussion of the state of nature', touches on a core area of psychological and political anthropology; in theological perspective, moreover, it bears a strong relation (in Genesis 2–5) to the gender dichotomy. Therefore, it will be reconstructed here in more detail. Weber's dichotomisation is under complex. *Status naturae* is more differentiated in scholastic theological literature, to which Weber refers terminologically; without an additional attribute, the 'naked' term *status naturae* is unfamiliar. Letelier Widow (2018, p. 201) points to four different uses of the figure of *status naturae* in scholasticism, two theological (1. and 2.), one political (3.), and one philosophical (4.):

1. The *status naturae innocens* is the paradisaical original state before the Fall of mankind (e.g., in Thomas Aquinas' *summa theologiae*).
2. The *status naturae post peccatum*, is the gender-dichotomous state after the Fall of mankind (so, for instance, literally in Molina; cited in Letelier Widow, 2018).

The evolutionary starting point and the inescapable dividing line between the two is the dialectical recognition of the sexual dimorphism of human existence, as a man (and insofar as not-woman) and as a woman (and insofar as not-man). Modern evolutionary theory, whether in biology, sociobiology, or evolutionary psychology, confirms sexual dimorphism as the conflictual dynamic 'engine' of human genesis and history: The evolutionary scarcity of the reproductive resource 'female uterus' versus the surplus of the reproductive resource 'male sperm' leads to the principle of *male competition versus female choice* (Buss, 2005; Voland, 1992, 2000). Both *status* experience a social-theoretical reinterpretation and dynamization only in modern times:

3. The *status naturae ante contractum* then becomes the hypothetical starting point of political contract and legitimation theories of modernity. In Thomas Hobbes and John Locke, they are **negatively** related to the *status naturae post peccatum* (2.), the (ideal) state/State stands here opposite sinful man, as 'tamer' of naturally evil human beings. Jean-Jacques Rousseau or Karl Marx later **positively** refer to the *status naturae innocens* (1.), the (existing) state/State stands opposite to this innocent man here, as an obstacle to otherwise naturally good human beings. 'Rousseau does not reproach Hobbes for describing the *state of nature* as a state of war, but instead for having it located at the *beginning* of human history, rather than at a *subsequent moment*. In doing so, Rousseau justifies his own triadic (and no longer dyadic) conception of history.' (Bobbio, 2016, p. 5, *italics* added).
4. In contrast, the *status naturae purae* is – negatively – a purely philosophical speculation, of a man surrounded only by his works, without the stigma of earthly sin nor the possibility of the *status gratiae* as divine grace (so again in Thomas Aquinas *summa theologiae*).

The first two figures (1. and 2.) are related to each other, so – to scholasticism – the state of original innocence is not (yet) apolitical opposite of society, but merely the theological counterpart of Christian sin. 'The innocent original state is not the counterpart of socialization, but simply the opposite of sin.' (Letelier Widow, 2018, p. 208) Moreover, both figures (that of paradise as well as that of chaos as the primordial state) have counterparts in Greek and Roman ancient mythology (for mythological, philosophical, and literary examples see Letelier Widow, 2018, p. 211).

In the medieval Joachim of Fiore, these *status* are interpreted in terms of historical philosophy and teleology as seven consecutive historical world epochs, as *status 1. iustitiae*, *2. patientiae*, *3. sapientie*, *4. gratiae*, *5.*

innocentiae [in that order], 6. *humilitatis profundae* and, finally 7. *probationis ultimae, et hic incipit tempore anticristi*. I will return to both *status* perspectives, the individual psychological and the historical-teleological.

It should be noted, for the sake of completeness, that beyond this (and contrary to it) an Aristotelian tradition assumes the general sociality of man, and to which state-of-nature speculations are unknown for this reason. If socialisation is 'natural' for man – as not only ζῷον πολιτικόν (political being), but ζῷον συνδυσαστικόν (sexually dimorph being) – the idea of a state of nature *ex ante* is meaningless, a hypothetical paradisiacal state of nature useless as a basis of the political one (Aristotle & Krapinger, 1993).

It is now interesting for our question that Max Weber strongly gendered these two *status* (*naturae* and *gratiae*, respectively). While his wife Marianne became a leading women's rights activist and politician in the Wilhelminian Empire, her husband explicitly paints a decidedly negative picture of female meaning-making through rationalising labour.

An image of backward traditionalist forms of work today is particularly often offered by women workers, especially unmarried ones. In particular, their absolute lack of ability and willingness to abandon outmoded and once learned ways of working in favour of other, more practical ones, (...) to learn and concentrate the mind or just to need it at all, is an almost universal complaint of employers who employ girls, especially German girls. (PEGK)

This is not an accidental remark that needs to be relativized and contextualised. Weber *expressis verbis* excludes reflections on the relationship between Protestant work ethics and women, when, a little later in the PEGK, he criticises that the *Realenzyklopädie für Protestantische Theologie und Kirche* under the keyword *Beruf* 'worthlessly, (...) instead of a scientific analysis of the concept and its genesis, contains all sorts of rather shallow remarks about all sorts of things, *women's question* [Frauenfrage], and the like.' (PEGK) 'Love' and 'greatness' are strictly counter-gendered in Weber's 'masculine thinking', according to Bologh (2009). The *status naturae* seems to suffice for women; proof of grace by proving oneself in one's profession is hardly ever sought by the latter, difficult for Weber himself to establish and imagine.

In contrast to this, there are the work-ascetic, Protestant men in the *status gratiae*, a spiritual aristocracy of the saints predestined by God from eternity in the world, an aristocracy which was separated with its character indelibility from the rest of humanity rejected from eternity [...] To this God-nobility of the elect [...] facing the sin of the neighbour, not indulgent helpfulness in the awareness of one's weakness was adequate, but hatred and contempt against him as an enemy of God, who bears the mark of eternal reprobation on himself. (PEGK)

Precisely because the *status gratiae* cannot be worked out, but on the contrary, success in work is only proof (not reason) of being chosen, Calvinistically predestined from the beginning, the *status gratiae* – according to Max Weber – has nothing to do with classical theological concepts like forgiveness and reconciliation, compassion and mercy.

The humanly understandable *Father in Heaven* of the New Testament, who rejoices over the return of the sinner like a woman over the recovered penny, has here become a transcendent being, withdrawn from any human understanding, who from eternity, according to completely inscrutable counsels, has assigned his fate to each individual and has disposed of everything smallest in the cosmos. (PEGK)

Weber's rhetorical-heroic, critical observations of feminism could also be interpreted in the context of the specific 'Protestant rationalism' of *fin de siècle* German universities, in which he faced fierce academic competition (on parallel rational routines and escape fantasies in Weber and Nietzsche see Treiber, 1992), but also in the context of the aforementioned political activity of his wife Marianne in the Baden parliament and especially in the women's movement, which he viewed ambivalently (see Krüger, 2001, and less convincingly Meurer, 2010).

To sum up: as ambivalent as his view of the gender dichotomy is Weber's diagnosis of Protestant ethics *in toto*. There was no recognisable alternative to nihilistic materialism, rational disenchantment and secularized asceticism, but instead of happiness they promised – as a 'grandiose consequence' (PEGK) - only material 'comfort', as a metaphor for confining an ethically acceptable 'comforting' lifestyle, and deep inner loneliness. Nevertheless, or precisely because of this, he categorically devalues those, who evade or are excluded from it in the *status naturae* (women and girls, for instance), without addressing or even resolving this contradiction.

Nussbaum's metaphysics of autonomising work

A hundred years have passed since then. Nussbaum revisits the Weberian narrative, deletes Weber's pessimism, and reverses the gender signs of the narrative. Her 'secularised-secularising work ethic as the spirit of feminism' be reconstructed and critically appreciated.

As a setting, she chooses India, whose social and historical structures may be unfamiliar in detail to most of her readers. The image of a backward, non-rationalised traditionalism, which Weber had still attributed to women, she now sketches oppositely – and in a tone not at all squeamish – for (Indian) men. "Male clerics play a big role in society, as in every country, and so, for example, Christian women in India got the right to divorce [...] only in the year 2001, because the different kinds of Catholic priests and Protestant ministers resisted change [...], it's ridiculous. [...] Muslim women [...] have a similar problem (with) a thing called the Muslim Personal Law Board, which is a bunch of unelected, self-perpetuating male clerics who decide what the rules should be, and because they're not accountable they don't listen enough to the voices of women." (Nussbaum & Kreisler, 2006)

In contrast, the experience of salvation through autonomising work is illustrated by her in the case of an (Indian) woman. Methodologically, in the following, I will deconstruct and then interpret the Calvinist-transcendental narrative underlying her story.

Vasanti, economically a lower-class woman, though of the highest traditional social *Brahma* caste, around 30 years of age, from Ahmedabad, is married to a 'gambler (and) alcoholic' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 1) who remains unnamed; her marriage remains barren and domestic violence leads, according to the narrative, to her leaving her husband and returning to her native family; so far, so commonplace-universal. A story of also personal failure and biographical regression, or of the emergence of new horizons of female autonomy? Her father is dead, and her brothers do not provide reliably and sufficiently for her, also the state of Gujarat 'had followed a growth-oriented agenda, without devoting many resources to the needs of its poorest inhabitants' (Nussbaum p. 9) – so, from where should help come? 'Many women in her position end up on the street, with no alternative but sex work,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 2).

The allusion to Luke 15:11–32, in the figure of the failed one in a foreign land seeking the way back to the merciful father, seems obvious. Also, the inaccessibility of this comforting-catching father figure, and the failure of his secularised form as 'father welfare state' takes *ex negativo* reference from this. The Calvinist narrative that Nussbaum so obviously employs boils down to the all-important question: Is Vasanti lost, even doomed like her ex-husband, or will she find her salvation – and how?

The moment of transformation comes from outside, and its effects are transcendent. 'Vasanti [...] discovered the Self-Employed Women's Organization (SEWA), a pathbreaking nongovernmental organization (NGO) in Ahmedabad that works with poor women.' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 2) SEWA itself shows all the ecclesiological signs of a true, almost religious-ascetic institution, *per Aspera ad Astra* – 'It began as a humble credit union, [but] now operates a bank in an impressive office building [...].'" (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 3) This is not surprising, since 'all the officers and employees of the bank are women, many of them former beneficiaries of SEWA's programs.' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 3) And, unlike in secular Indian society out there, 'divisions along lines of caste and religion are anathema in the Indian women's movement,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 3) A new community through work, female work. And an ascetic, pure community; sexual desires, for example, are not an issue among the righteous, on the contrary, 'divisions along lines of sex' are *essentialistically* charged to the dividing line between the chosen and the doomed:

They [the SEWA-employees] want to be able to live without a man, and they love the fact that one of SEWA's central ideals is the Gandhian notion of self-sufficiency. The thought is that, just as India could not win self-respect and freedom without achieving self-sufficiency from its colonial master [i.e., England], so women cannot have self-respect and freedom without extricating themselves from dependence on their colonial [sic] masters, namely, men [...] [They] express a preference for solidarity with a group of women. (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 11)

This, unintentional, silliness of the pathetic phrase can hardly be overlooked, that the author nevertheless aims at an agreement with the reader can only mean that they are established as *topoi* and need no explanation, but want to be recognized. Stylistically, the exoticism is unmistakable.

Which (a) individual psychological and which (b) historical-philosophical narrative underlies Nussbaum's text? In terms of the philosophy of history, it is about the decolonial narrative: Self-sufficiency then means, politically, statehood under international law and economic independence, in the concrete case the detachment of India, Pakistan and Bangladesh from the English crown, triggered by the demonstrative violation of the salt monopoly by the Mahatma Gandhi. This decolonisation is obviously to be understood as a historical-teleological necessity, a historical process that was on the one hand historically inevitable, but on the other hand also difficult and therefore to be actively pursued, and to which there was ultimately no alternative.

Post-colonialist narratives can be connected here, which construct the after-effects of colonialism and the unfinishedness (never: unfinishability) of the process. The establishedness of the historical-teleological narrative of the 'one' decolonisation towards national self-respect, freedom under international law and economic self-sufficiency is now analogised into an individual-psychological narrative: Vasanthi has had to free herself from – so literally – colonisation by her husband to become civilly divorced-independent, psychologically liberated, and economically self-sufficient. Freedom and independence, the narrative continues, thus become preconditions of solidarity. India's history and Vasanti's biography thus follow the same teleology.

The concept of solidarity could now appear as somehow 'burned out' because of the failed Marxist narrative and its historical crimes, especially in its proximity to the propagated metaphysics of labour. Therefore, it is immediately specified that it is about the preference for solidarity with a group of *women* (see above). Translated into Weberian terminology: the protagonist can assure herself of her saving salvation from the *status naturae post peccatum* up to her *status gratiae*: through work, female-solidary gainful employment. Nussbaum's choice of words 'extricating oneself' gives her otherwise rather sober-pragmatic narrative a stylistic, almost Old Testament flavour; it is about saving, tearing oneself out in the greatest need, to extricate oneself. The exotic, Biblicistic tone of the Calvinist pastor, who tells her congregation about the temptations and the steadfastness of the tested soul, is unmistakable, as is the danger of drifting stylistically into the clichéd and silly.

Modestly, perhaps even a bit self-deprecatingly, Nussbaum concurs 'storytelling is never neutral; the narrator always directs attention to some features of the world rather than to others,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 15) These other features of the world concern the dark side of Vasanti's salvation, the contrasting side of men.

Manichaeisation of the biological gender dichotomy

For Nussbaum's untheorised, naive propagation of the autonomous, female subject, who becomes aware of her *status gratiae* in work, inspires a complementary, extremely pejorative anti-male rhetoric. Female metaphysics of work and a corresponding, sexual asceticism are contrasted with male 'gambling and drinking' in an almost caricature-like black-and-white manner. The Calvinist question of salvation and the election is reduced – and this is what is specifically modern about Nussbaum – to a simple gender issue, predestined from the beginning, therefore obviously neither accessible to nor in need of an in-depth analysis. Her White, Protestant, partly feminine, partly feminist values are transformed, wrapped in exoticist garb, into globalised political activism and cultural messianism without reflecting on their genesis, history, contexts, or limits. Clark rightly criticises that Nussbaum 'bestows and takes away "fundamental entitlements" with alarming regularity and ease.' (Clark, 2013, p. 177)

So, what about her husband, what is the cause of his addiction to alcohol and gambling, the Calvinist epitome of a self-imposed *status naturae post peccatum*? In Nussbaum's pre-modern narrative, the reader learns nothing about this. 'He got a vasectomy to take advantage [sic] of the cash incentive that Gujarat's government offered to encourage sterilisation,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 2); a proactive loser, that's all the reader is supposed to know. Alas, what has gone wrong in his life that he has allowed the State to buy a central credential of his male identity for a few rupees; perhaps even to save his marriage? Doesn't this poor wretch deserve our sympathy and perhaps even pity, living as he does in the same miserably hopeless conditions as his wife, conditions so near-distant and exotically-attractive for Western academics? One might ask as a reading listener. Where does he turn, from where does help come to him? Nussbaum's narrative here becomes one of unprecedented cynicism: She considers the vasectomy of this nameless and faceless divorced husband to be quite problematic as such; but only for *others*, for 'vasectomy is not a great means of population control for many reasons, not the least of which is that it robs women [sic] of choice,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 8) It is hard to speak more pejoratively sexist about any human being, man or woman. One of the well-sounding axioms of the otherwise dogmatically and methodologically unrounded *Capabilities Approach* is that anthropologically the means-purpose relation must always turn out in favour of the latter, 'the approach

espouses a principle of each person *as an end.*' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 35, *italics* original). Nussbaum could hardly have formulated her restriction in a more sexist-cynical way, for it implicitly applies only to women: Women are ends, men are means. Now, what exactly makes the nameless husband so doomed and untouchable, alcohol and gambling addiction alone?

Only apparently gender-neutral, Nussbaum states: 'the toll that *domestic violence* takes on physical health is enormous, but its effect on emotional health is equally devastating.' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 8, *italics* added) It is hard to disagree with this, the emergence of a spiral of domestic violence from (a) psychological to (b) physical to the invocation of (c.) state-structural violence is quite well explored in the criminological and forensic literature: Violence in general, but especially domestic violence, is thereby, according to prevailing opinion, not a freely chosen evil, therefore primarily ethically reprehensible, and certainly gender-specific, but on the contrary, it is dependent on various interdependent variables such as biographical imprint, family system, social class, age, sexual orientation, reproductive status of men and women, also drug use, communication skills, intelligence, ethnicity or religion, but especially sexual fidelity and infidelity, suspected and/or real. And domestic violence leaves deep feelings of powerlessness and anger, of shame and guilt, of remorse and despair. Central to our context is: all variables apply equally to men and women, women and men (for a systemic approach to domestic violence, see extensively and forcefully Hamel & Nicholls, 2007; Bock, 2003; Krahé, 2003).

Empirically wrong, moreover, is Nussbaum's explicit assessment that children protect women from domestic violence by men by their very existence, 'a childless woman is more vulnerable to domestic violence.' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 2) Perpetrators of domestic violence against children are 80% women, simply because they are empirically much more involved with children daily, therefore many more situations arise for violence to occur (Bock, 2019). However, again, domestic female violence against children is not 'freely chosen evil' either, but is also an expression of excessive demands and powerlessness, disillusionment and helplessness on the side of the mother or professional.

Between adult partners, it is difficult to separate perpetrators and victims; Hamel & Nicholls (2007) assume a 50/50 distribution in their meta-analysis. Nussbaum, on the other side, constructs an uncompromisingly bleak, masculine background apart from these criminological findings, from which the rescue of her female protagonist stands out all the brighter. There is no room for an enlightened-rational view of the emergence of violence in close social relationships, especially as a function of social class; it is about something greater, something higher – the struggle of good and evil, the rescue of the innocent, the death of the dragon (criminologically sober on this ancient figure still paradigmatic-criminal Lüderssen, 1999). Whoever inquires there, critically soberly, even doubts unflinchingly, probably almost makes himself an accomplice (Popp, 2003). Since the issue is central to Nussbaum's gender Manichaeism, we have deconstructed it at length here and will return to the issue again.

In the same pastoral Calvinist tone, Nussbaum concludes by turning the gaze back to the big picture to reinforce the work ethic in the face of the world's imperfection without resignation, no matter where the individual sincere may live; Vasanti (and even more perhaps her male counterpart) is everywhere: 'All nations [...] are developing nations [...]. All are currently failing at the aim of ensuring dignity and opportunity for each person [sic].' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 16) We are all sinners, some more, some less.

This is hardly scientifically meaningful to contradict, but it still does not represent a social-theoretically founded, empirically falsifiable, innovative approach to psychological and political issues of development. On the contrary, Nussbaum's narrative is at best fairy-tale and romantic-childish, at worst misanthropic-cynical, 'she ultimately has nothing to fall back on but her own *refined intuitions,*' (so ironically Clark, 2013, p. 177, *italics* added). Thus, in an exotic land, she finds exactly what she was looking for: backwards-violent villains and helpless-good *bonnes sauvages* (for historical reconstructions of these *topoi* and their political implications, see Cro, 1990; also Jahoda, 1999).

Her pastoral intellectual tone is highly missionary and arrogant, her maternal gestures of disposition and exclusion toward her informant Vasanti and her informant's ex-husband, especially in this cross-cultural context, completely methodologically untenable, logically unsound, and psychologically exposing. Methodologically, as it neither recognizably follows the established logic of social science research nor makes explicit and justifies alternative methods (Döring & Bortz, 2016; Kowal & O'Connell, 2010). Logically, as her Capabilities list existentialistically assigns and denies by gender without being able to justify (see below). Psychologically exposing her pastoral 'paternalism-individuals and countries may choose to realise capabilities in a variety of ways, but they cannot challenge any of the items on Nussbaum's list.' (Clark, 2013, p. 178; see also Okin, 2003) Nussbaum seems convinced that what the poor have missed most in their lives is

the transcendent interference of the white Anglo-Saxon Protestant missionary "from the outside" - in his secularized, modernized-feminine version, to be sure.

Dependent wage labour, however, organised and paid, is the stigma of the many, not the distinction of the few, and it usually does not promise religious purification and transcendence, as Nussbaum's hagiography insinuates, but simply consumes a lifetime. To confuse the sublime with work enharmonically is in and of itself, the historical process, which Weber reconstructs so vividly and by no means affirmatively, and which still demands more explanations, legitimations and reflections than it provides answers; and which certainly does not automatically compel missionary action. Outside of strict Calvinism, work is precisely *not* a metaphysical or eschatological principle that can only be finally concretised and applied. In the narrative to which Nussbaum refers, work ethic is originally more a stigma into which we immerse our burdened selves than a divine response to the *conditio humana* that should only be greeted with joy. Weber himself sighed resignedly, 'the Puritan wanted to be a professional man, we must be.' (PEGK)

Nussbaum's Calvinist work ethic and the spirit of feminism

Nevertheless, Nussbaum's capability approach stands out restfully from the almost mediievally unworldly, speculative feminist scholasticism of, say, a Judith Butler (Nussbaum, 1999).

A still slightly expanding Indian population not only wants to be fed but also demands life opportunities and social advancement on a globalized scale. Counteracting (also religiously based) *quietism* and resignation here seems sensible. India's poverty rate has been more than halved in recent years, the literacy rate among young people is now over 90%, the proportion of the population living in extreme poverty was only 3% in 2019, the total population is no longer growing fast, and a Western-style middle class is emerging in many parts of the subcontinent (World Bank, 2020). Vasanti's rudimentary middle-class stratification itself is part of this development. If Nussbaum's CA has contributed to this - which would have to be shown - it would be to be welcomed without hesitation.

To be rejected, on the other hand, is her moralistic gender Manicheism, which is inseparable from the rhetoric of her Capabilities Approach. She summarises her emphasis on 'changes for real people' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 14) as 'working with many activists over the years and noticing what their experienced eyes notice as significant in the lives of women of their societies, I have tried to educate my judgment accordingly [...]' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 15)

This demonstrative attention to exclusively female biographies, even their messianic historical-teleological charge as part of liberation from patriarchal 'colonisation', on the other hand, must itself be critically deconstructed as a missionary feminist narrative. This applies to its historical-teleological-collective as well as to its biographical-individual side. Neither is Vasanti's everyday story of marital failure inscribed in a historical or metaphysical collective-female struggle against patriarchy nor does her gender absolve her from processing her parts as perpetrator and victim in coming to terms with social and emotional experiences of marital failure, however poor or wealthy she may be.

Weber had no illusions about the high costs of a capitalist society based on the division of labour; at that time borne by men. The loneliness that accompanied the competition for resources during lifelong gainful employment was countered as consolation only by 'comfort', which 'characteristically (spans) the circle of ethically permissible uses [...], clean and solid,' (PEGK). Nussbaum takes up the motives but turns them into their opposite.

Not gainful employment, but on the contrary, her marriage had isolated Vasanti, 'during her marriage she was cut off all relationships except the highly unequal one with her abusive husband.' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 9) Now, however, she is 'active in politics, [...] [with] a whole group of friends who respect her as an equal.' Compared to a socio-educationally supervised female gainful employment in a (presumably subsidised) NGO, the intimacy of marriage, especially sexual intimacy, appears here as depressing, provisional, violent, and demeaning, especially also in connection with the extensively described political consciousness-raising that accompanies Vasanti's divorce. The contact with the SEWA NGO is itself logically presented as a kind of religious revival experience, 'a sign of new openness and curiosity. She seemed excited and proud to talk about her *new life*.' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 9, *italics added*).

In any case, her friend Kokila (for whom it remains unclear whether she is a work colleague or caretaker of the NGO) and Vasanti become political activists, 'combating domestic violence in her community [...], a key issue,'

(Nussbaum, p. 3/4). Two physically weak but mentally strong female lights in the diffuse darkness of male-dominated violence in distant patriarchal lands, unapproachable to our steps.

The narrative of liberation on this individual psychological level is now equally extended to a historical-teleological model of development. Central again is the woman's possibility to improve her social status through a divorce, to gain 'bargaining power in the marriage' and 'leverage against an abusive husband,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 8). The central moment in Nussbaum's narrative separating men and women is the violence argument.

Violence, it is implied, is categorically counter-gendered between men and women according to perpetrators and victims. So axiomatic is this assumption that Nussbaum neither explicates it theoretically nor verifies it empirically; put another way: Falsification, or even differentiation, of this assumption, would bring down her argument. It underlies both Vasanti's salvation narrative and her absurd manicheisation of CA itself. With the topic of divorce, she brings her exoticist narrative into the lifeworld horizon of her readers, and especially female readers of the Western academic middle class. 'The experience of domestic violence is probably as common in the US as it is in India, studies show, and strategies to combat it are still insufficient [...], (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 16). Even though she does not list any theoretical derivation and/or empirical data for this idea, so the reader does not know what is specifically meant by 'studies show', one will agree. However, this experience of domestic violence affects men and women equally, both as perpetrators and as victims (on children and domestic violence, see above). Nussbaum's CA is therefore not suitable for a social-theoretical approach to development, whether in a psychological, a nation-state framework or international cooperation. It is the opposite.

The narrative of the liberating effect of the dissolution of marriages and families and their replacement by female autonomous gainful employment, whether subsidised in an NGO or on the free human capital market, is gender lobbyism by Western academics on their behalf, needily cloaked in exoticist garb. On the one hand, because it narratively rationalises individual psychological guilt and shame over marital failure into female narratives of purification and absolution. Second, because it materially-concretely defines children as the lifelong 'property' of mothers in terms of natural law, but at the same time gives property and compensation issues in divorces in favour of women a central place in its CA. In this respect, the gain of female autonomy through gainful employment is not supposed to affect older social equalization and provision mechanisms. Their narrative is not about justice-theoretical *equality for all*, but about gender-lobbyist *at least equality for us*.

Lobbyism is the CA also because Nussbaum consistently ignores the voices of (married) men. The voice of Vasanti's ex-husband remains mute – his name, his biography, his traditional caste, his subsequent fate as a divorced, sterile alcoholic and gambling addict – not a word. The category of 'traditional caste' seems worth mentioning insofar as it could be an indicator of a traditional *mesalliance*, an indicator of the lack of satisfaction of the female need for hypergamy, in other words, the inability to fulfil Vasanti's status claims as a Brahmin (for a detailed discussion of the antagonism between political-philosophical desires for equality and emotional desires for hypergamy, see Meier, 2018). Again, Nussbaum's narrative merely exoticizes Western feminist discourses of divorce and hypergamy, of education and income. Her central syllogism is deconstructed in this respect:

What I found was that of course, the issues are continuous with issues that feminists talk about in the US – sexual harassment, domestic violence, adequate rape laws, these are big issues – but there are also quite other issues [...], like *girls* being able to go to school, *girls* being able not to be married at age six, *girls* being able to have access to employment opportunities, being able to have equal property rights. These things are very connected with the others because one main way that women can stand up to their husbands against domestic violence is by having a job so that the husband knows that she can exit if she wants to, she can take that money out of the household, [...] and then, 'I'm losing, (Nussbaum & Kreisler, 2006, *italics* added)

Seemingly classically syllogistic, the recall of the established 'big issues' of psychological and physical, exclusively male violence is followed by the antithetical infantilisation of the corresponding women as 'girls' who prefer to go to school and work instead of getting married at age 6, and 'these things are very connected.'

Schematically, it could be presented like this:

Major premise	Men can be	violent (psychologically and physically).
Minor premise	(School-)girls are	not men.

From both sentences, no conclusion can be formed since the premises are not sufficiently defined. Statements about analogous adult women (instead of girls) and their (potential or actual, psychological, physical and/or structural-state) violence, possibly theoretically derived and empirically proven, are missing.

Nevertheless, Nussbaum implicitly draws the following conclusion:

Conclusion	Women cannot be	violent (psychologically, physically, nor structurally - ergo: 'guilty' .
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Strictly Aristotelian-social-democratic, however, this conclusion could have been reached only by stating the following propositions, since only in this way logical subject and logical predicate with corresponding *termini maior, medius* and *minor* would have been present:

Major premise	Exclusively men	<u>can be/are violent.</u>
Minor premise	Women are	not men.
Conclusion	Women	cannot be <u>violent/are not violent.</u>

Nussbaum's, empirically evidence-free, linking of exclusively male psychological ('sexual harassment'), physical ('domestic violence', 'rape') and the invocation of state-structural violence ('The legal system is slow and notoriously corrupt'; Nussbaum, 2011, p. 8) is logically inconclusive, the narrowing of the topic of marriage and family to (male) violence and (female) divorce serves as a kind of ethical free license with exoticist colouration. In any case, the exaggeration of the aporias of Western gender lobbyism into a developmental-historical-teleological demasculinisation narrative is naïve at best, silly at worst, but in any case deeply sexist and unjust, the plain opposite of a new 'theory of justice' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 18).

Plea for an Aristotelian social democracy

Nussbaum herself anticisationally invokes Aristotle as a guarantor of her project of universalist women's autonomy. This seems somewhat bold in terms of philological interpretation. Aristotle does not know any fantasies of the natural states; therefore he does not fantasise about liberation as social programmes, one-sidedly gendered, state-subsidised ones either. Discussions about one or more *status naturae* are alien to him (in detail see Knoll, 2009). To his political anthropology, man is, as said, not only ζῷον πολιτικόν (political being) but ζῷον συνδυαστικόν (sexually dimorph being), a being that is always and exclusively the result of a preceding social relationship of man and woman thus, *tertium non datur* (Aristotle & Krapinger, 1993). A paradisiacal primordial state is unknown to Aristotle, its recovery as a political programme; however naïve and/or politically dangerous – un-Aristotelian, if only when dichotomously biologised. Justice, on the contrary, is Aristotle's famous definition in the Nicomachean Ethics of treating equals equally and unequals unequally. (Aristotle & Krapinger, 1993; socio-theoretically by Gordon, 2007)

Thus, the central question becomes: What are men and women, what our fathers and mothers – equal or unequal? According to Aristotle, this depends on the applied standard, so also with the question about the equality and inequality of men and women, fathers and mothers. For traditionally they are biologically – reproductively complementary-unequal, and traditional societies like India treat them (or treated them until recently) unequally for this reason, in family and inheritance law, for example, but also in the military. Nussbaum attempts to scandalise this, with little cultural sensitivity, by portraying 'unequal laws of property and inheritance,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 4) as regressive from a Western feminist perspective. The implicit basis of this social and legal inequality, however, was the notion of a biological inequality of the sexes, which in its complementarity – and only in this complementarity – ensured the physical-biological continuity of society and the State, and only in this way.

Economically-productively, on the other hand, men and women are in principle equal, if one ignores minor differences in body size (Hines, 2005) and intelligence dispersion (Nyborg, 2005). Modern societies with a certain obsession for economic production, therefore, treat men and women equally, even see the 'active enforcement of equality as a Constitutional goal' (Grundgesetz, n.d.), diverging only in the question of whether equality of opportunity, procedural equality or equality of outcome is meant (Hegtvædt & Cook, n.d.; Konow, 2003; McCorkel et al., 2005; Tyler & Allan Lind, 2002).

Left unresolved, indeed: untheorized, is the question of reproductive inequality, and with it that of the demographic reproduction of society and the State. Implicitly, this is solved in the CA in terms of natural law: children are understood as a lifestyle addition and lifelong property of the mother, '(providing) her with a source of love,' (Nussbaum, 2011, p. 9). This untheorized natural law distribution of rights and duties, burdens and joys between the two biologically complementary-unequal parents can hardly be justified in terms of justice theory. It cannot work, and it does not work, neither in India nor in the West, neither in mediated nor in poor societies. Instead, the economy-induced absolutisation of gender autonomy leads to a demographic imbalance that is already abundantly evident in all Western societies. Biological reproduction becomes an incalculable financial, social and not least emotional life risk, especially for young men, who avoid it for good reasons.

An Aristotelian social democracy, in contrast, would bid farewell to the obsession with increasing economic production through the autonomisation of the sexes 'at all costs' and would insist on the inescapable, natural, and sustainable reproductive complementarity of the two sexes as ζῆλον συνδυσαστικῶν. It would understand the long, parental-investment-intensive phases of childhood and adolescence and the associated need for declining, especially female, economic productivity no longer as a welfare-state nuisance that 'non-violent' models of autonomous female parenthood and wage labour would have to remedy in equal measure, but as part of the human condition, whose evolutionarily anchored need for constant biological renewal the modern, production-oriented state - in contrast to the traditional, reproduction-oriented state - does not sufficiently account for.

Thus, instead of propagating female autonomy and work as a progressive, and - on the discursive detour via the violence narrative - the only just model of society, it would seem more promising and more fruitful to (re)base the enlightened constitutional discussion directly on the anthropological fact of complementary sexuality as *status naturae purae*. This would require and release both socio-philosophical and constitutional-legal imagination, which would not get lost in rationalizing exotisms and redundant moralistic rigorism. To vary a famous dictum of the German social philosopher Karl Marx (1818–1883), it would be important to turn Nussbaum's Aristotle 'from its head to its feet' to weigh the costs and benefits of the propagated race to catch up in terms of female modernization, rationalisation and disenchantment.

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